

THE AVAILABILITY OF ASCORBIC ACID OF SHADDOCK (*CITROUS DECUMANA*) BY ADULT HUMAN SUBJECTS

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The availability of vitamin-C of shaddock was determined by experiments on three healthy students of age 20 to 23 years. Response to doses of ascorbic acid varied from subject to subject. The average urinary excretions of ascorbic acid of the three subjects on a daily dose of 75 mg. of crystalline ascorbic acid were found to be 47.4, 41.3 and 45.7 mg. and on a daily dose of 25 mg. of the crystalline acid and 50 mg. vitamin-C from shaddock juice. These were found to be 50.2, 41.3 and 44.5 mg. respectively. It is concluded that the availability of vitamin-C of shaddock is of the same order as that of the crystalline ascorbic acid.

Much work has been done regarding the vitamin-C content of Indian fruits, vegetables and other foodstuffs, but there is no literature about their availability by Indian adult. The purpose of the present investigation is to study the availability of vitamin-C of shaddock, a citrus fruit, by direct metabolic experiments on human subjects.

Very little work has been done in this line of human nutrition. Hawley, Stephens and Anderson (*J. Nutrition*, 1936, 11, 135) by studying with orange juice, Todhunter *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1940, 19, 121) with lemon juice and raspberries, Clayton *et al.* (*J. Home. Econ.*, 1940, 32, 390; *J. Nutrition*, 1943, 25, 349) with potato, raw cabbage and canned tomato juice, and Hartzler (*J. Nutrition*, 1945, 30, 355) with papaya and guava found that the vitamin-C of the above foodstuffs was as well utilised as that in pure crystalline form.

'Zambura' or 'Batapi Lebu' (*Citrus decumana*), also called grapefruit, shaddock and pomalo in English, is a cheap citrus fruit found abundantly in India and contains a fairly large amount of ascorbic acid in its juice (45 to 60 mg./100 c.c.). Because of cheapness and the presence of a considerable amount of ascorbic acid in it, this fruit was chosen for the present investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL

The method used in the present study was similar to that adopted by Clayton and Borden (*J. Nutrition*, 1943, 25, 349) with some modifications. In their investigations the subjects were resaturated after the control period before the experimental period, but in the present investigation the subjects were tested for saturation after the completion of the control and experimental periods.

The experiments were carried out in following periods :—

Preliminary adjustment period.—Each subject was given 300 mg. of ascorbic acid* per day for 3 days before starting the experiment, the experimental periods were as follows :

* Redoxon tablets (Roche products) received by the courtesy of Messrs Volkart Brothers, Bombay.

Period-1. Saturation period (duration, 7 days).—The subjects were on the basal diet plus 200 mg. of vitamin-C daily (two 50 mg. tablets at breakfast and another two at lunch).

Period-2. Control period (duration, 7 days).—The subjects were on basal diet plus 75 mg. of vitamin-C daily at breakfast. The purpose of this period was to determine to what extent saturation could be maintained by 75 mg. of the pure vitamin.

Period-3. Experimental period (duration, 7 days).—The subjects were on basal diet plus 25 mg. of vitamin-C and the amount of shaddock juice required to provide 50 mg. of vitamin-C. The purpose of this period was to determine to what extent the vitamin-C of the shaddock juice supplemented by the 25 mg. of vitamin-C in tablet form would maintain saturation and how the results would compare with those secured in period-2.

Period-4. Saturation-test period (duration, 2 days).—The subjects were on basal diet plus 200 mg. of vitamin-C daily as in period-1. The purpose of this period was to test if the subjects were in a state of saturation throughout the control and experimental periods.

TABLE I

Urinary excretion (24 hours) of vitamin-C (in mg.)

Periods	Subject	Subject	Subject	Subject	Subject	Subject	Subject	Subject	Subject	Subject	Subject
	No. I.	No. II.	No. III.	No. I.	No. II.	No. III.	No. I.	No. II.	No. III.	No. I.	No. II.
	Saturation period			Control period			Experimental period			Saturation test period	
1st day	226.8	103.0	146.5	94.4	45.3	84.0	77.9	58.0	60.0	115.2	94.0
2nd day	105.6	78.1	115.0	45.1	64.0	48.0	72.6	42.0	48.0	130.0	112.3
3rd day	129.9	87.4	152.5	64.4	38.0	60.5	32.5	51.2	58.0	—	—
4th day	149.6	94.6	107.0	45.1	56.0	32.5	58.1	37.0	37.0	—	—
5th day	154.9	114.7	136.4	50.2	31.0	49.0	61.0	42.0	—	—	—
6th day	110.0	103.0	103.5	32.0	45.5	38.5	42.5	33.0	—	—	—
7th day	139.7	108.9	140.5	45.5	36.0	48.0	57.0	43.5	—	—	—
Mean of the last 5 days	136.8	101.7	128.0	47.4	41.3	45.7	50.2	41.3	44.5*	—	—

*The mean value of 3rd and 4th days excretion.

The experiment was conducted on three college students residing in hostel and they were kept on restricted diet providing on average less than 5 mg. ascorbic acid daily. The diet was fed *ad libitum* and consisted of boiled rice, mashur dal, fish, *patol* and boiled cow's milk. Other vitamins were provided in the form of tablets twice daily to supply the requirement. As the vitamin-C content of the shaddock juice varied in almost every fruit, the juices were analysed every day before they were given as experimental doses.

Urine excreted during 24 hours was collected in brown (2500 c.c.) glass-stoppered bottles containing enough oxalic acid to bring the acid concentration of the final volume to 0.5%.

All ascorbic acid determinations were made with 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol in the photoelectric colorimeter by the method of Loeffler and Ponting (*Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1942' 14, 846).

D I S C U S S I O N

Results of the experiments are shown in Table I from which it is observed that on ingesting 200 mg. ascorbic acid to the students in the saturation period, immediately after the preliminary adjustment period with 300 mg. dose, the subjects I, II and III during 24 hours excreted 105.6 to 226.8 mg., 78.1 to 114.7 mg. and 103.5 to 152.5 mg. ascorbic acid in urine respectively. Since 300 mg. dose of the preliminary adjustment period might have influenced the urinary excretions of the first two days of the saturation period following it, only the last five days' collection of the saturation period was taken into consideration and their average values 136.8 mg., 101.7 mg. and 128 mg. respectively for the subjects I, II and III have been presented in the table. As these average values were more than 50% of the intake, the subjects were therefore regarded as saturated. Since lower test dose of 200 mg. saturated the subjects, the higher test dose was not applied.

After saturation, when 75 mg. of crystalline ascorbic acid were given in the control period, the daily urinary excretion of ascorbic acid of the subjects I, II and III for the last five days of the period ranged from 32 to 64.4 mg., 31 to 56 mg. and 32.5 to 60.5 mg. with the mean values of 47.4, 41.3 and 45.7 mg. respectively.

In the experimental period, when the subjects were given 25 mg. of crystalline ascorbic acid and a quantity of shaddock juice (generally 80 to 100 c.c.) required to furnish 50 mg. of vitamin-C, the daily urinary output of the vitamin by subjects I and II was found to range from 32.5 to 61.0 mg. and 33.0 to 51.2 mg. with the mean value of 50.2 and 41.3 mg. respectively for the last five days' excretion period. As the subject no. III fell ill after the 4th day of the experimental period, the experiment on that subject was discontinued after that day and the average value of 44.5 mg. of the 3rd and 4th days' excretions has been shown in the table.

To test whether the subject remained saturated after the control and experimental periods, they were given 200 mg. test dose of crystalline ascorbic acid for 2 days. The subjects were found to respond to this dose satisfactorily. The urinary excretions of vitamin-C on the 2nd day were found to be 130 and 112.5 mg. for the subjects I and II respectively. As these eliminations exceeded 50% of the total intake, the subjects were considered to have remained saturated during the whole control and experimental periods.

Survey of the data presented in the table shows that the average urinary excretions

of ascorbic acid in the experimental period exceeded that in the control period by +2.8 mg. for subject I, by 0.0 mg. for subject II, and by -1.2 for subject III. The negative value in the case of the subject III may be due to comparatively short experimental period. As the differences in the mean values of the urinary excretion of vitamin-C by the subjects in the experimental and control periods are not large, it may be concluded that the ascorbic acid of shaddock is as well utilised as the crystalline vitamin-C.

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